

1 **Supporting Information for**

2 **Ecosystem metabolism and nitrogen budget of a glacial fjord in the Arctic**

3
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31

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42 **Text S1**

43 **Upscaling of denitrification and nitrification**

44 Summer and annual nitrification and denitrification rates were upscaled from spring field
45 observations¹. These authors performed field measurements of denitrification and nitrification on
46 three days in March (beginning, mid, and end of March), in the upper 50 m of the water column.
47 Water samples were collected from stations Kb1 to Kb5 (Fig. 1). The water temperature ranged
48 from -2.8 to 0 °C. Nitrification (denitrification) rates were measured by chemically blocking
49 denitrification (nitrification) during incubation at ambient temperature (2 - 0.5°C). Additional
50 incubation experiments were run to determine the sensitivity of both processes to daylight.
51 Denitrification rates were not sensitive to daylight length, but nitrification was inhibited with
52 increasing daylight hours (Fig. 6 in Ref. ¹ and Table S3). Therefore, we assume that nitrification
53 at the top 50 m is active only during the polar night (criteria for polar night was 24h dark), which
54 was estimated as 115 days / 2760 hours, using the online tool
55 https://aa.usno.navy.mil/data/Dur_OneYear. Nitrification was assumed to be active throughout
56 the year (8760 h) in the volume of water below 50 m, which is likely to receive no light [e.g.,
57 Refs. ^{2,3}). Denitrification, on the other hand, was assumed to be active throughout the year at a
58 constant rate below and above 50 m. These rates and the fjord volume, estimated using the
59 K160_bgc model grid and bathymetry within the area depicted in Fig. 1c (Kongsfjorden as
60 delimited by the white line), were used to upscale nitrification and denitrification spatially and
61 temporarily, based on field and laboratory incubations (Table S4). We consider the rates to be
62 constant throughout the year, although temperature likely affects these rates. As shown by
63 Krishnan et al. ¹, nitrification and denitrification rates are positively related to temperature and
64 can double at 12°C water temperature.

65 $TN = [Vol \times Rate \times H]$ (S1)

66 where TN is the total nitrogen contribution from each process, Vol is the volume of the water
67 layer of interest, H is the number of hours per year (or polar night in the case of nitrification
68 above 50 m) or in summer (July-August).

69 **Text S2**

70 **Phyto- and zooplankton fluxes**

71 We estimated phytoplankton and zooplankton nitrogen fluxes based on stock values for these
72 organisms in the outer region of Kongsfjorden (Table 1 in Ref. ⁴, and references therein) that
73 were converted to concentrations based on known depths, and MOSJ chlorophyll concentration
74 data for stations Kb0 and Kb1. These data were combined with the volume transport across the
75 transect depicted in Fig. 1c (white line delimiting Kongsfjorden) from model simulations (see -
76 Methodology - Model description and Text S5), similar to the computation of nutrient fluxes.
77 Chlorophyll was converted to carbon using a C: Chlorophyll ratio of 50 [e.g. Ref. ⁶].
78 Phytoplankton stocks ranged from 0.35 to 5.3 g C m⁻² and were converted to nitrogen assuming
79 the Redfield mass ratio (C: N=5.7). The AMUST-KB3 dataset (Table S1) includes chlorophyll
80 concentrations, particulate organic carbon (POC), and nitrogen (PON) for several samples. The
81 average C: Chlorophyll ratio was 147 and the average POC: PON was 7.8. However, it is
82 difficult to assess the contribution of detritus and zooplankton to these ratios. Therefore, we have
83 chosen to use the literature values mentioned above. Regarding zooplankton, we used a stock of
84 12 g dry weight (DW) m⁻², obtained from samples collected at station Kb0 (Table 6 in Ref. ⁴).
85 We also used more recent estimates based on sampling with a WP2 net (mesh size of 180 µm) at
86 station Kb1 (Fig. 1c) in 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023. The average zooplankton stock was

87 estimated as 19 g DW m^{-2} , using a dry mass conversion factor derived from literature values (see
88 Supplementary Table 1 in Ref. ⁵). Dry weight values were converted to nitrogen using 0.08 g N g
89 $(\text{DW})^{-1}$ ⁶.

90 **Text S3**

91 **Kelp distribution and standing stock**

92 Kelp standing stock was estimated using published high-resolution seafloor light⁷ and summer
93 biomass data along a depth transect (Tables S1 and S2 in Ref. ⁸). We first estimated the area of
94 potential kelp presence using the light threshold of $47 \text{ mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ [Ref. ⁹]. Then, we
95 used depth-to-biomass data to obtain a relationship, which was applied to the potential kelp areas
96 to estimate the biomass gradient from the nearshore to greater depths (details in Table S5, and
97 Fig. S6). Finally, biomass was integrated over depth and area to obtain the standing stock
98 existing within the fjord area defined in Fig. 1c. The kelp bottom percentage coverage variability
99 was used as a proxy for biomass variability to obtain the standing stock range. The carbon and
100 the nitrogen content in the dry weight of kelp was estimated using published averaged values for
101 *Saccharina latissima*: 36% C and 1.4% N of DW, which were derived from seven fjords in the
102 Arctic (Table 1 in Ref. ¹⁰).

103 The depth-biomass relationship was established using averaged dry weight measurements (g DW
104 m^{-2}) of three kelp species (*Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima* and *Laminaria digitata*) in
105 2012 and 2013 at discrete depths (0, 2.5, 5, 10, and 15 m) along an inshore to offshore transect in
106 Hansneset, Kongsfjorden (Ref. ⁸, Tables S1 and S2). The curve fitting method was the piecewise
107 polynomial (function PCHIP in Matlab <https://www.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/pchip.html>;
108 Refs. ^{11, 12}).

109 The curve is constructed by fitting biomass data to each depth range (piece) independently. Each
110 piece thus represents a section of the curve, having its own set of coefficients (Table S5). In our
111 example (Fig. S6) we added two artificial points at 20 and 50 m depth to force the curve to a 0
112 value. The data were then interpolated from 0 to 50 m depth at 0.5 m intervals using the obtained
113 PCHIP function for each depth range.

114 The kelp bottom coverage in the region where the biomass data was obtained was estimated at
115 45% (Area n. 6 in Table 1 of Kruss et al. ¹³) and it varied between 17 and 62% in other regions
116 along the coast of Kongsfjorden (Areas n. 5 and n. 2, respectively, in Table 1 of Kruss et al. ¹³).
117 Therefore, the 17 to 62% range in kelp cover becomes 38% and 135% when scaled to the
118 percentage cover at Hansneset. Thus, the standing stock was multiplied by 0.38 and 1.35 to
119 obtain the lower and the upper range, respectively. In this way we adjust our potential estimates
120 to reflect the scarcity of hard substrata and/or the presence of sea urchins (Kruss et al. ¹³).

121 **Text S4**

122 **Nitrogen consumption by birds**

123 We used our own published data on daily energy expenditure for 11 seabird species in
124 Kongsfjorden [e.g. Refs. ^{14, 15}]. The estimate was made for breeders, non-breeders, and chicks
125 during their residence time in Kongsfjorden. The annual food requirement for the Kongsfjorden
126 seabird community is approximately 426 tonnes y^{-1} (wet weight) (considering the most recent
127 bird population estimates). Since ~70 % of the food is taken from Kongsfjorden, birds consume
128 ~298 tonnes y^{-1} (wet weight) of food from the fjord. The carbon consumption was estimated
129 from the food consumption, assuming a dry mass: wet mass ratio of 1/3 and a carbon content of
130 40 % ⁴. Carbon consumption was converted to nitrogen assuming a C: N mass ratio of 3.4, based

131 on values for polar cod (*Boreogadus saida*) and capelin (*Mallotus villosus*)¹⁶, which are
132 common seabird prey in Kongsfjorden¹⁷. To obtain summer daily consumption rates, we
133 assumed that most seabirds stay in the fjord from 15 May to 15 August⁴.

134 **Text S5**

135 **K160_bgc model**

136 The basic properties of the 3D numerical model setup, including the extent of the model domain,
137 horizontal resolution (160 m), number of vertical (sigma) layers (35), and bathymetry used in
138 this study, are the same as described in the “present-day scenario” by Torsvik et al. [Ref. ¹⁸] (Fig.
139 S2a).

140 Our model configuration includes changes in relation to the that described by Sundfjord et al.¹⁹,
141 detailed by ¹⁸ (i)-(iii), plus those specified below (iv-v): (i) the model domain extends further
142 west and not so far to the north as the configuration described in ¹⁹; (ii) the coastline has been
143 adjusted using the S100 Svalbard map dataset²⁰; (iii) the terminuses of the tidewater glaciers
144 correspond to their locations in 2009; (iv) an analytical plume model was coupled with the ocean
145 model to simulate the upwelling of the subglacial discharge plumes and the associated
146 entrainment of fjord water²¹ and (v) we use spatially variable Jerlov optical water types²², based
147 on photosynthetically active radiation data and light extinction coefficients reported in ²³ (Fig.
148 S2b). We used the same atmospheric and oceanic forcings, and boundary conditions described in
149 ¹⁸.

150 The high-resolution atmospheric fields used to force the model over the period Sept. 2006 –
151 Sept. 2007 were provided by the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF), developed by

152 the National Center of Atmospheric Research (NCAR). The WRF model is a state-of-the-art
153 numerical weather prediction model²⁴, and its implementation includes a domain with a
154 horizontal grid resolution of 3 km. The model was initialized with an analysis (on a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$
155 grid) of upper air and surface data from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather
156 Forecasts (ECMWF), and lateral boundary values were updated every 6th hour during
157 integration.

158 Ocean boundary conditions were obtained from a two-layer one-way nested model system
159 comprising a Pan-Arctic model at 4 km horizontal resolution (A4 model) and a smaller model at
160 800-m resolution (S800 model), described in ^{19, 25}. Daily averages from the A4 model are used to
161 provide open boundary conditions for the S800 model domain, and tidal forcing for both A4 and
162 S800 is provided by the global tidal model TPXO v7.2 [Ref. ²⁶; <https://www.tpxo.net/global>].
163 Hourly output from S800 is used to define boundary conditions for K160_bgc, hence the inner
164 nested layer does not make use of a separate tidal model. The K160_bgc simulations are carried
165 out with a 4-month spin-up period (Sept.–Dec. 2006), followed by a 9-month simulation period
166 (Jan.–Sept. 2007). The reason for using these conditions for 2007 is the availability of many
167 salinity-temperature profiles in Kongsfjorden for that year, which are adequate for evaluating
168 simulated salinity-temperature profiles.

169 We plotted a sample of the vertical profiles of salinity and temperature bias for some of the
170 stations depicted in Fig. 1. Generally, temperature and salinity biases were $< 1^\circ\text{C}$ and < 0.2 ,
171 respectively (Fig. S3). Taylor diagrams²⁷ were produced based on comparisons between model
172 results and > 300 CTD salinity and temperature vertical profiles²⁸ (Fig. S4). We also made
173 comparisons with the results of the S800 model providing the boundaries to the K160_bgc
174 model. The Centred Root Mean Square Difference of the former is larger than that of the latter,

175 whereas the opposite is true for the correlation coefficient between observations and model
176 results. Moreover, the standard deviation of the K160_bgc model is closer to that of the
177 observations. The results show that the higher resolution K160_bgc model performs better than
178 the S800 model and that part of its bias is “inherited” through the S800 boundary conditions.

179 The K160_bgc simulation evaluated here was also used to compute the fjord flushing time (FT),
180 as described below. The FT is a bulk parameter describing the exchange characteristics of a
181 waterbody without identifying the underlying physical processes, their relative importance, or
182 their spatial variability (e.g. Ref. ^{29, 30}). There are different ways to calculate FT ²⁹, such as V/Q
183 (where V is the system volume and Q is the volumetric flow rate). However, this approach
184 assumes that the waterbody is a continuously stirred tank reactor²⁹. To avoid such simplified
185 assumption, we used forward simulations to compute FT as described in ³⁰ and detailed below.

186 To estimate FT, K160_bgc simulations were run for spring/summer periods (after a spin-up run
187 of > 2 months) using a passive tracer with an initial concentration of 1 inside the fjord (area
188 delimited by the white line in Fig. 1c) and above 100 m depth. Elsewhere, the concentration of
189 this passive tracer was set at zero. This depth range was chosen for compatibility with the range
190 used to calculate tracer concentration gradients and NEM (cf. - Methodology - Analysis of
191 nutrients/DIC concentration gradients and quantification of biogeochemical sinks/sources). Then
192 we ran the model and monitored the tracer decrease over time (e.g. Ref. ³⁰). The tracer
193 concentration decreases with time, but it never reaches zero. Therefore, some threshold
194 concentration must be chosen as a criterium to calculate FT. Here we set it at 40% of the original
195 concentration and FT was calculated as the number of days required to flush out 60% of the
196 original amount of the tracer, following Edwards and Sharples’ study in a fjord in Scotland³¹
197 (equations S1 and S2). We expect the FT to vary with tidal amplitudes, freshwater discharges²⁹

198 and boundary conditions. Therefore, to consider this variability, we ran more simulations, using
199 more recent years. For that purpose, we used boundaries provided by the S500 model (Text S6).
200 The availability of boundary conditions from larger scale simulations limited our own
201 simulations to spring-summer 2007 and 2019.

$$202 \quad TracerContent_{day} = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k (x_{ijk} V_{ijk}) \quad (S1)$$

203 Where i, j , and k are grid indexes used to sum up the tracer contents in each model grid cell for
204 each simulated day.

$$205 \quad TracerFraction_{day} = \frac{TracerContent_{day}}{TracerContent_1} \quad (S2)$$

206 $TracerContent_1$ is the amount of tracer at the beginning of the simulation.

207 **Text S6**

208 **S500 model**

209 The S500-model system (Fig. S5) is used to provide the open boundary conditions for the
210 K160_bgc for 2019 simulations. The setup is based on ROMS-version 3.5 [Refs. ^{32, 33, 34}],
211 including a simple sea-ice model introduced by Budgell³⁵. The bathymetry-following vertical
212 coordinate system is defined by the same 35 sigma-levels used in K160_bgc, while the
213 horizontal model grid has a fixed resolution of 500 m and covers the entire Svalbard archipelago.
214 Lateral boundary conditions and tidal forcing are applied using data from the Norwegian
215 Meteorological Institute (MET Norway)'s operational ocean forecasting model Barents2.5³⁶.
216 Atmospheric forcing time series stem from MET Norway's operational atmospheric forecasting
217 model AROME-Arctic AA, 2.5 km horizontal resolution, Ref. ³⁷. Daily runoffs from freshwater

218 sources are based on simulations with the CryoGrid land surface model, forced with AROME-
219 Arctic as well [Refs. ^{38,39}].

220 When using boundaries provided by the S500 model for the K160_bgc simulations we use the
221 same forcings of the former model, except for the glacier discharges that were taken from ⁴⁰.

222

223 **Tables S1 to S9**

224 **Table S1.** Datasets used in this study.

Data sets	Survey	Dates	References
Calleja et al.	Seasonal transect cruises (nutrient profiles along Kongsfjorden)	May, August, and October 2012	41
Monitoring of Svalbard and Jan Mayen program (MOSJ)	Transect cruises (CTD and nutrient and DIC profiles between the deep eastern Fram Strait and inner Kongsfjorden)	July-August 2011-2020	42, 43, 44, 45
Torres-Valdes et al.	Moorings with remote access nutrient samplers	August 2016 – August 2017	46
AMUST-KB3	Biogeochemical and ecophysiological monitoring at station Kb3 in Kongsfjorden	April and May 2014, 2016-2018	47
AMUST-transects	Transect cruises (CTD and nutrient profiles)	April and May 2016-2018 and 2021	
AWIPEV underwater observatory	Ferry box system measuring nutrient concentrations	April 2014-May 2018	48

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227

228 **Table S2.** Definitions of water masses in Kongsfjorden following ⁴⁹.

Water mass	Abbreviation	Potential temperature (°C)	Salinity (psu)
Atlantic water	AW	>3.0	>34.65
Arctic water	ArW	-1.5 to 1.0	34.30 to 34.80
Winter-cooled water	WCW	<-0.5	34.40 to 35.00
Local water	LW	-0.5 to 1.0	34.30 to 34.85
Surface water	SW	>1.0	<34.00
Transformed Atlantic water	TAW	1.0 to 3.0	>34.65
Intermediate water	IW	>1.0	34.00 to 34.65

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234 **Table S3.** Denitrification and nitrification rates ($\text{ng L}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) from Fig. 6 in Ref. 1.

	Field measurements	Experiment rate in light $\text{ng L}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$	Experiment rate in dark
Denitrification	3.3	6.5	7.5
Nitrification	1.6	0	2.3

235

236

237 **Table S4.** Contribution of nitrification and denitrification to the nitrate pool (tonnes N summer⁻¹
 238 or tonnes N y⁻¹) in Kongsfjorden based on field measurements and on laboratory incubations.
 239 Denitrification is not sensitive to light, but nitrification is only active in the dark. To calculate
 240 nitrification, we consider only the number of hours without daylight in summer and per year.
 241 Water depths below 50 m are assumed to be in the dark.

Year		Summer (July and August)		
	Based on field measurements	Based on incubation experiments	Based on field measurements	Based on incubation experiments
Surface (0 - 50 m)				
Denitrification	280	595	48	101
Nitrification	64	93	0.3	0.4
Net contribution	-215	-501	-47	-101
Deep layer (50 m to seafloor)				
Denitrification	526	1115	89	189
Nitrification	255	366	43	62
Net contribution	-271	-748	-46	-127
Total (0 m - seafloor)				
Denitrification	806	1710	137	290
Nitrification	319	459	43	62

Net contribution	-487	-1251	-94	-228
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243

244 **Table S5.** Coefficients for the piecewise polynomial function (PCHIP) to fit the biomass along
 245 the depth gradient.

Interval: $x_1 - x_2$	Coefficients $\times 10^4$			
(m)	a	b	c	d
0 - 2.5	-0.0058	-0.1636	0.9269	0.1908
2.5 - 5	0.1119	-0.4433	0	1.3949
5 - 10	-0.0005	0.0137	-0.1185	0.3727
10 - 15	0.0001	0.0009	-0.0198	0.0588
15 - 20	-0.0000	0.0000	0.000	0.000
20 - 50	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.000	0.000
Equation form: $f(x) = a(x_2-x_1)^3 + b(x_2-x_1)^2 + c(x_2-x_1) + d$				

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247

248 **Table S6.** Biogeochemical ammonium *Sources-Sinks* estimated with equation 1, based on
 249 average salinities and concentrations of ammonium in AW found in the shelf stations V10, V12,
 250 and V14, in the top 100 m, and comparable values in IW, SW or AW found in the fjord stations
 251 Kb1-Kb5, and using $1.44 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ for the freshwater endmember.

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Ammonium Sources-Sinks ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$)			
Year	AWs versus IW	AWs versus SW	AWs versus AWf
2013	0.9	0.10	1.6
2014	0.8	0.43	2.0
2015	0.0	-0.3	0.7
2016	0.9	0.98	1.8
2017	0.7	0.43	1.4
2020	0.9	0.65	1.3

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263 **Footnote:** Refer to Methodology - Freshwater inputs, for nutrient concentrations in freshwater
 264 and Table S2 for water-mass classification. Subscripts s and f are used to distinguish AW in the
 265 shelf and in the fjord, respectively. Values in bold correspond to significant concentration
 266 differences between the water masses (two-tailed t-test, $p < 0.05$).

267

268 **Table S7.** Biogeochemical phosphate *Sources-Sinks* estimated with equation 1, based on average
 269 salinities and concentrations of phosphate in AW found in the shelf stations V10, V12, and V14,
 270 in the top 100 m, and comparable values in IW, SW or AW found in the fjord stations Kb1-Kb5,
 271 and using $0.064 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ for the freshwater endmember.

Phosphate Sources-Sinks ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$)			
Year	<i>AWs versus</i>	<i>AWs versus</i>	<i>AWs versus</i>
	IW	SW	AWf
2011	-0.2	-0.1	-
2012	-0.2	-0.3	-0.2
2013	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1
2014	-0.3	0.0	0.0
2015	-0.2	-0.6	-0.3
2016	-0.6	-0.6	-0.3
2017	-0.1	-0.2	0.1
2018	-0.1	-0.1	0.2
2019	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1
2020	-0.2	-0.3	0.0

272 **Footnote:** Refer to Methodology - Freshwater inputs, for nutrient concentrations in freshwater
 273 and Table S2 for water-mass classification. Subscripts s and f are used to distinguish AW in the
 274 shelf and in the fjord, respectively. No data is marked by the dash “-” symbol. Values in bold
 275 correspond to significant concentration differences between the water masses (two-tailed t-test, p
 276 < 0.05).

277 **Table S8.** Biogeochemical silicic acid *Sources-Sinks* estimated with equation 1, based on
 278 average salinities and concentrations of silicic acid in AW found in the shelf stations V10, V12,
 279 and V14, in the top 100 m, and comparable values in IW, SW or AW found in the fjord stations
 280 Kb1-Kb5, and using $9.77 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ for the freshwater endmember.

Silicic acid <i>Sources-Sinks</i> ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$)			
Year	AWs <i>versus</i> IW	AWs <i>versus</i> SW	AWs <i>versus</i> AWf
2011	-0.9	-1.5	-
2012	-2.2	-2.5	-2.3
2013	-0.4	-1.1	-0.2
2014	-1.6	-1.3	-0.6
2015	-2.1	-2.5	-0.5
2016	-1.8	-1.7	-0.4
2017	-1.0	-0.9	0.8
2018	-1.5	-1.5	0.0
2019	-1.6	-1.1	-0.2
2020	-1.4	-1.8	-0.2

281 **Footnote:** Refer to Methodology - Freshwater inputs, for nutrient concentrations in freshwater
 282 and Table S2 for water-mass classification. Subscripts s and f are used to distinguish AW in the
 283 shelf and in the fjord, respectively. No data is marked by the dash “-” symbol. Values in bold
 284 correspond to significant concentration differences between the water masses (two-tailed t-test, p
 285 < 0.05).

286 **Table S9.** Biogeochemical nitrate + nitrite *Sources-Sinks* estimated with equation 2, based on
 287 average salinities and concentrations of nitrate + nitrite in AW found in the shelf stations V10,
 288 V12 and V14, in the top **50 and 150 m**, and comparable values in IW, SW or AW, found in the
 289 fjord stations Kb1-Kb5. These estimates assume 2.0 $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ for the freshwater endmember.
 290 No data is marked by the dash “-” symbol. Refer to paper Methodology- Freshwater inputs for
 291 nutrient concentrations in freshwater and Table S2 for water mass classification.

Nitrate + nitrite <i>Sources-Sinks</i> ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$)						
Estimates based on top 50 m				Estimates based on top 150 m		
Year	AW	AW versus	AW versus	AW versus	AW versus	AW versus
	versus	SW	AW	IW	SW	AW
	IW					
2011	-2.0	-1.2	-	-2.0	-1.2	-
2012	-3.8	-4.0	-4.1	-4.9	-5.0	-5.2
2013	-1.8	-2.4	-0.7	-3.7	-4.2	-2.6
2014	-3.7	-3.1	-3.2	-4.7	-4.0	-2.6
2015	-4.9	-5.2	-2.4	-7.5	-7.7	-4.4
2016	-4.3	-4.1	-3.2	-5.3	-5.0	-2.5
2017	-2.4	-2.3	-0.8	-3.3	-3.2	0.5
2018	-0.5	-0.7	-	-1.7	-1.8	1.9
2019	-2.8	-2.6	-2.6	-4.0	-3.7	-2.9
2020	-3.3	-3.9	-2.5	-4.7	-5.2	-1.8

293
 294 **Figure S1.** Example of a nutrient-salinity diagram including the concentration at the freshwater
 295 endmembers (green dots at zero salinity), in the marine endmember [Atlantic Water (AW), blue
 296 crosses and dots] and, in Intermediate Water (IW, red crosses and dots) inside the fjord. Dots are
 297 arithmetic averages of the data represented by the crosses of the same color. These averages were
 298 used in equation 1 for the various terms. The symbology used here is the same as in equation 1.
 299 Refer Table S2 for the definition of the various water masses.

301

302 **Figure S2.** (a) K160_bgc model domain and bathymetry [color scale corresponding to depths in
 303 meters (m)], showing Kongsfjorden, Krossfjorden and the adjacent coastal area; (b) Jerlov water
 304 types used in this study: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 correspond to types I, IA, IB, II and III [e.g. Ref. ⁵⁰].

305

306 **Figure S3.** Model temperature and salinity biases from CTD profiles for stations shown in Fig. 1

307 in the main text. Only depths greater than 10 m are considered.

308

309 **Figure S4.** Taylor diagrams based on results from >300 CTD profiles collected in 2007 for
 310 salinity (a) and temperature (b), and results from the S800 and the K160 models, where the
 311 boundaries of the latter are interpolated from the results of the former model. The red line depicts
 312 the standard deviation of the observations. CRMSD stands for Centered Root Mean Square
 313 Difference.

314

315

316

317 **Figure S5.** Domain and bathymetry of the S500 model used to provide boundary conditions
 318 for the K160_bgc model (2019 simulations).

319

320

321 **Figure S6.** Distribution of kelp biomass along a depth gradient at Hansneset, Kongsfjorden.

322 We forced the biomass at 20 and 50 m to be 0 to maintain low biomass values at depth.

323

324

325

326 **Figure S7.** Contours of absolute salinity (top) and conservative temperature (bottom) for 2019
 327 (a-b) and 2020 (c-d) from the MOSJ dataset for the Kongsfjorden summer transect, and water
 328 masses delimited by the black lines, according to ⁴⁹ (AW – Atlantic Water, TAW – Transformed
 329 Atlantic Water, SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water). A subset of the sampling
 330 stations is plotted over panels a, c. Refer to Table S2 for water mass characteristics and Fig. 1b, c
 331 for the location of all sampling stations. The white areas in the contour plots correspond to places
 332 where data were not available. In the case of station Kb5 there were no data below 100 m due to
 333 depth constraints.

334

335

336 **Figure S8.** Nitrate + nitrite-salinity diagrams for the whole sampling period based on summer
 337 MOSJ data. Blue circles contain data from all water masses found in the study area, whereas red
 338 crosses are only for SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water (refer to Table S2 for
 339 water mass characteristics).

340

341 **Figure S9.** Dissolved inorganic carbon-salinity diagrams for the whole sampling period based on
 342 summer MOSJ data. Blue circles contain data from all water masses found in the study area,
 343 whereas red crosses are only for SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water (refer to
 344 Table S2 for water mass characteristics).

345

346 **Figure S10.** Ammonia concentration contours ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) for 2013-2017 and 2020 based on
 347 MOSJ dataset for the Kongsfjorden summer transect, and water masses delimited by the black
 348 lines, according to ⁴⁹ (AW – Atlantic Water, TAW – Transformed Atlantic Water, SW – Surface
 349 Water, and IW – Intermediate Water). A subset of the sampling stations is plotted over panels a,
 350 d. Refer to Table S2 for water mass characteristics and Figs. 1b, c for the location of all sampling
 351 stations. The white areas in the contour plots correspond to places where data were not available.
 352 In the case of station Kb5 there were no data below 100 m due to depth constraints.

353

354

355 **Figure S11.** Ammonia-salinity diagrams for the whole sampling period based on summer MOSJ
 356 data. Blue circles contain data from all water masses found in the study area, whereas red crosses
 357 are only for SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water (refer to Table S2 for water mass
 358 characteristics).

359

360 **Figure S12.** Phosphate concentration contours ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) for 2011 - 2020 based on MOSJ
 361 dataset for the Kongsfjorden summer transect, and water masses delimited by the black lines,
 362 according to ⁴⁹ (AW – Atlantic Water, TAW – Transformed Atlantic Water, SW – Surface
 363 Water, and IW – Intermediate Water). A subset of the sampling stations is plotted over panels a,
 364 f. Refer to Table S2 for water mass characteristics and Figs. 1b, c for the location of all sampling
 365 stations. plotted over panels (a) and (f). Refer to Table S2 for water mass characteristics and
 366 Figs. 1c, d for the location of all sampling stations. The white areas in the contour plots
 367 correspond to places where data were not available. In the case of station Kb5 there were no data
 368 below 100 m due to depth constraints.

369

370 **Figure S13.** Phosphate-salinity diagrams for the whole sampling period based on summer MOSJ
 371 data. Blue circles contain data from all water masses found in the study area, whereas red crosses
 372 are only for SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water (refer to Table S2 for water mass
 373 characteristics).

374

375 **Figure S14.** Silicic acid concentration contours ($\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) for 2011 - 2020 based on MOSJ
 376 dataset for the Kongsfjorden summer transect, and water masses delimited by the black lines,
 377 according to ⁴⁹ (AW – Atlantic Water, TAW – Transformed Atlantic Water, SW – Surface
 378 Water, and IW – Intermediate Water). A subset of the sampling stations is plotted over panels a,
 379 f. Refer to Table S2 for water mass characteristics and Figs. 1b, c for the location of all sampling
 380 stations. The white areas in the contour plots correspond to places where data were not available.
 381 In the case of station Kb5 there were no data below 100 m due to depth constraints.

382

383 **Figure 15.** Silicic acid -salinity diagrams for the whole sampling period based on summer MOSJ

384 data. Blue circles contain data from all water masses found in the study area, whereas red crosses

385 are only for SW – Surface Water, and IW – Intermediate Water (refer to Table S2 for water mass

386 characteristics).

388

389 **Figure S16.** Nitrate + nitrite data from the MOSJ, AMUST and Torres-Valdes et al. [Ref. ⁴⁶]
 390 datasets for stations outside Kongsfjorden (F4-S-1 and HG-IV-S-1, magenta squares) and inside
 391 Kongsfjorden (Kb3) and from the AWIPEV dataset (Ferry Box, also inside Kongsfjorden and
 392 close to Kb3), all the other symbols (refer Table S1 and Fig. 1). Concentration shown in μM
 393 instead of $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ due to the lack of salinity data for some of the datasets.

394

395

396

397 **Figure S17.** Results from a simulation between 01.06.2007 and 31.07.2007. (a) Change in the
 398 tracer contents within the fjord relative to day 1 of the simulation, calculated with equation S2.
 399 Black vertical lines mark the time needed for the flushing of 60 and 90% of a tracer (~15 and
 400 ~28 days, respectively). The first threshold was used as proxy to the fjord flushing time. (b)
 401 Spatial variability of flushing time of surface water (0-100 m) in Kongsfjorden.

402

403 **Figure S18.** Results from a simulation between 01.04.2019 and 23.06.2019. (a) Change in the
 404 tracer contents within the fjord relative to day 1 of the simulation, calculated with equation S2.
 405 Black vertical line marks the time needed for the flushing of 60 and 90% of a tracer (~10 and
 406 ~30 days, respectively). The first threshold was used as proxy to the fjord flushing time. (b)
 407 Spatial variability of flushing time of surface water (0-100 m) in Kongsfjorden.

408

409 **Figure S19.** Results from a simulation between 23.06.2019 and 05.09.2019. (a) Change in the
 410 tracer contents within the fjord relative to day 1 of the simulation, calculated with equation S2.
 411 Black vertical line marks the time needed for the flushing of 60 and 90% of a tracer (~10 and
 412 ~12 days, respectively). The first threshold was used as proxy to the fjord flushing time. (b)
 413 Spatial variability of flushing time of surface water (0-100 m) in Kongsfjorden.

414

415

416 **Figure S20.** Yearly averaged atmospheric nitrogen loads (see text).

417

418 **Figure S21.** (a) Daily subglacial and surface glacier river flows from the model of van Pelt et al.

419 [Ref. ⁴⁰]; (b) Yearly averaged nitrogen loads with the river flows. The dashed line marks the year

420 of 2011, which is the beginning of our study period (see text).

421

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